

VET ED AND THE BIG QUESTIONS

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People who know me in real life also know that I am active in educational communities in Community Engaged Learning (CEL). But like all educational practices, CEL is a means to an end, not a goal on its own. Why do I think CEL can add to VetEd? **CEL is an educational approach that can inspire engagement with relevant societal issues in moving toward sustainable and healthy futures, and provides learning ground for veterinary medicine students to work together constructively with stakeholders who may have different goals or views than their own.**

Increasingly, society looks to veterinarians to use their expertise to guide discussions on key societal and civic issues. This is seen at the national level within the Netherlands as expressed in a report commissioned by the Ministerie van Landbouw, Natuur en Voedselkwaliteit (Ministry of Agriculture, Nature and Food Quality) on the current and future role of veterinarians in the Netherlands (1), as well as in initiatives like Caring Vets and Vet Sustain which emphasize the role of veterinarians in sustainable transitions. Taking the cow by the horns, so to speak (see photo- yes, dairy cattle also have horns, these are nearly always removed in a painful

procedure in calves because they don't fit in current dairy cattle farming systems- which is one of those difficult conversations vets should have).

Veterinarians have a special place in society. The general public view veterinarians as a trusted source of scientific information (3), who are knowledgeable about and should be able to communicate and discuss complex issues like climate change and its effects on animals and humans. As professionals, veterinarians have both access to scientific information and insights, and also direct communication with stakeholders (ie farmers, commercial parties, lay public) (4). Despite this clear role that veterinarians can play, and feel called toward (5), veterinarians are not yet as well represented in societal discussions surrounding for instance sustainability issues as they could be, which is a missed opportunity for both veterinarians and society.

So how can we as VetEd professionals contribute to preparing veterinarians to take up this role? There is a need to further build on communication, leadership and community building skills in the veterinary medicine curricula to equip future veterinarians to take on leadership roles in complex questions like One Health, One Welfare, and sustainability transitions (6,7). Here is where viewing curricula through a CEL-lens can help. A key concept in CEL is reciprocity (see my [earlier post on the concept of reciprocity](#)); understanding where another person is approaching an issue from can help enormously in engaging in discussion about The Big Questions and wicked problems without easy solutions.

Contact with lay public is an essential part of CEL and a natural component of VetEd; clinical work almost by definition means contact with owners, farmers, and other lay public. In further development of Vet Ed programs, we should build more on that contact and give our vets tools to have these complex discussions in a constructive and empathetic manner by teaching reciprocity and having students reflect upon the role of veterinary professionals in these interactions. CEL experience and practice can help us further this reciprocity and reflection in Vet Ed.

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